

**COPING WITH THE COVID-19 EDUCATION CRISIS:
AN INVESTIGATION OF THE EXPERIENCES AND
CHALLENGES OF PARENTS IN SUPPORTING
DISTANCE LEARNING**

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Coping with the COVID-19 Education Crisis: An Investigation of the Experiences and Challenges of Parents in Supporting Distance Learning

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Abstract

This study contributes to the growing body of literature on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on basic education in the Philippines by investigating the experiences and challenges faced by parents in supporting their children's distance learning. The study used a qualitative research approach and semi-structured interviews with ten parents chosen via purposive sampling. The investigation revealed five significant themes: changes in parents' daily routines, an absence of formal teaching training, challenges accessing technological resources, learning with their child, and gratitude for educators and the education sector. The findings underscore the pandemic's considerable impact on the daily lives of parents and their children, as well as the difficulties parents have in assisting their children's learning due to a lack of formal education training and access to technology. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the beneficial results of distant learning, such as deeper and more meaningful interactions between parents and their children, as well as parents' recognition for educators' efforts in responding to the pandemic's challenges. The report finishes with practical recommendations for educators and politicians on how to effectively support families in distress.

Keywords: *parental involvement, educational challenges, COVID-19 pandemic, distance learning*

Introduction

During the pandemic, the Philippines was one of the countries utilised online learning as a backup to in-person classes. The country's education industry has been affected, particularly among public institutions, which are more sensitive to the digital divide and lack the essential infrastructure to facilitate distant learning (Jubair, 2020). Private schools have been quicker to adjust to the new educational standard, but they confront their own set of obstacles, particularly in assuring educational quality and student involvement. The abrupt transition to remote learning has brought various issues for students, teachers, and parents who must now support their children's education from home (DePasquale, 2020).

With the transition to distant learning, parents have taken on a larger role in their children's education. The pandemic has compelled parents to become more involved in their children's education, especially in ensuring that their children have access to the technology and resources required for online lessons. The Philippine Department of Education acknowledges the vital role of parents in the new normal education and has reiterated the significance of their engagement in providing facilities such as gadgets and internet access for their children's education (Malipot, 2020). Parents are expected to guarantee that their children's education continues despite any difficulties.

As the COVID-19 pandemic has had a huge influence on traditional schooling, there has been a shift toward distance learning. Distance learning, according to Li and Lalani (2020), is an alternative to traditional face-to-face instruction that makes use of digital technologies to promote student-teacher contact, content distribution, and learning activities. The closing of educational institutions, social distancing requirements, and the necessity to safeguard the health and safety of students, instructors, and staff all demanded this transformation. While this strategy has its drawbacks, it has also created possibilities to experiment with new methods of teaching and learning, as well as the potential to revolutionize the education system in the long run (Panda et al., 2020). Most schools are adopting a hybrid of modular and online classes based on the screen time allotted in each grade level to maintain instruction during the pandemic. Parents can pick whether their child will attend only modular classes or a combination of modular and online classes. This arrangement, however, presents a tremendous difficulty not just for the pupils but also for the parents. In the new normal system, parents are expected to have a larger role, including explaining and teaching their children the lessons they may not grasp during their online classes.

Inequalities in access to instructional materials, such as textbooks and other learning tools, can potentially be exacerbated by distance learning (DL). Schools can assist close the gap by giving students access to digital textbooks and other online learning materials. Schools

can also collaborate with publishers and other groups to deliver these products for free or at a reduced cost (Education Trust, 2020). Students from low-income households or those experiencing housing insecurity may lack access to peaceful, comfortable study rooms as well as a stable internet connection. In other situations, these children may also be responsible for younger siblings or other family members, making it difficult to concentrate on education. Schools and communities can help to address these gaps by offering additional support services such as homework assistance, tutoring, and mentoring programs (Lei & Gupta, 2021). Many students lack access to distant learning technology and resources, such as computers, internet connection, and educational software. Schools and communities can assist alleviate these inequities by giving children access to these resources, either through loan programs or partnerships with technology companies and internet service providers (Education Trust, 2020).

DL requires learners to study from home utilizing multiple technologies and online platforms, and it increases parents' obligation to support their children's learning (DePasquale, 2020). Parents have de facto taken on the role of teachers, organizing their children's schedules, offering technical aid, and guaranteeing their children's involvement and motivation (Katz, 2020). Many parents, particularly those who are balancing employment and other commitments, have expressed stress and worry as a result of this new responsibility (Cao et al., 2020). Since distant learning has become the new status quo in education, little is known about the experiences and problems of parents in supporting their children's learning during the pandemic. Parents have become de facto teachers, managing their children's schedules, providing technical assistance, and ensuring their children's engagement and motivation (Katz, 2020). This new role has caused stress and anxiety for many parents, particularly those who are juggling work and other responsibilities (Cao et al., 2020).

Quite apart from the difficulties, parents, instructors, and students in the Philippines have demonstrated perseverance and adaptability in continuing to study during the pandemic (Jubair, 2020). Yet, little is known about parents' experiences and issues with remote learning in the Philippines. Exploring parents' experiences and challenges in supporting distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippines can provide a better understanding of the perspectives of parents with children in public or private schools in the country, as well as identify potential solutions and interventions to assist parents

in managing the new normal of education.

The objective of the study is to examine the experiences and challenges of parents in the Philippines who are helping their children with their schooling during the peak of the COVID-19 outbreak. The study aims to identify the specific obstacles that parents encounter, investigate their perceptions of their capacity to assist their children's learning, investigate how they balance the demands of supporting their children's education with other duties, identify the sorts of help and resources they require, assess their interactions with teachers and school officials, and identify the potential long-term consequences of the epidemic on parent engagement.. Ultimately, the study aims to provide practical insights and recommendations for how educators and policymakers can better support families during times of crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Literature Review

The Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on Education

Nationwide lockdowns have been enacted in several nations, including the Philippines, posing difficulties for the government in assuring children's ongoing learning during the pandemic (Chang & Yano, 2020). As a result, governments and educational institutions around the world have turned to remote learning methods such as the internet and other online platforms, as well as massive open online courses (MOOC) (Chang and Yano, 2020). To ensure that children's learning continues, a collaborative effort between the telecom industry, school networks at all levels, and the education service is required (UNESCO, 2020). To promote justice and inclusivity in education, certain nations such as China and South Korea are offering devices and resources to students who do not have access to the internet, while some countries like France and Japan are caring for students who cannot be taken care of at home (Chang and Yano, 2020; Giannini and Lewis, 2020). Furthermore, parental involvement in their children's learning through online tutoring systems has been proposed to strengthen the link among parents and children while also reducing children's anxiety and tension during these uncertain times (Wang et al., 2020).

A curriculum that combines parental counseling and coronavirus-related understanding is required to promote learning success in home settings to improve the execution of the education system during the

pandemic (Chang and Yano, 2020). Such programs can also help children develop their own study skills and establish a sense of responsibility for their own growth and development. Overall, the epidemic has unmistakably emphasized the necessity of education and the need to adapt to changing circumstances. Despite the pandemic's obstacles, attempts are being made to guarantee that children's education continues, with governments and educational institutions shifting to distance learning methods and supporting inclusiveness and equity in education. As a result, for many pupils, distant learning has become the new norm, with parents propelled into the position of facilitators of learning. During the epidemic, the value of parental involvement in remote learning cannot be stressed. A UNESCO (2020) study discovered that parental involvement in distant learning was favorably connected with students' academic progress. Furthermore, during these unique times, parental engagement was proven to be critical in providing emotional support and a suitable learning environment for their children (Malipot, 2020). As a result, parents' role in assisting their children's remote learning during the epidemic is critical for academic performance and overall well-being.

The pandemic has exposed the differences in access to technology and internet connectivity among children, instructors, and schools. Pupils from low-income households and those living in rural regions are more likely to have limited access to technology and the internet, resulting in a digital gap. Additionally, students with impairments and those who require specialized services suffer severe difficulties in accessing proper DL support. These injustices have caused existing achievement gaps to expand, worsening the accomplishment gap between pupils of different socioeconomic backgrounds. The abrupt move to DL has presented difficulties for both pupils and teachers. Several students have reported feeling detached and isolated from their friends and professors, resulting to lower engagement and enthusiasm to learn. Furthermore, the change to DL has had an impact on the quality of education, with some students having less learning chances due to a lack of resources and support. As a result, some academics are concerned about the pandemic's long-term implications on student learning results as well as their social and emotional well-being.

Educators and policymakers have used a variety of ways to lessen the pandemic's impact on education. They include providing low-income students with technology and internet access, implementing remote learning support services for students with

impairments, and using alternate means of assessment to evaluate student learning results. However, the usefulness of these strategies is still being investigated, and more study is needed to determine their efficacy. Ongoing study is needed to develop effective measures to lessen the effects of the epidemic on education, particularly on DL.

Role of Parents as Facilitators of Learning

Parental involvement is essential for children's academic performance, and remote learning offers new opportunities and challenges for parental involvement. Parents may assist their children study at home by establishing routines, providing a designated learning place, evaluating their progress, and communicating with teachers (Kim, 2020). Parental involvement has been linked to enhanced academic outcomes for students, such as higher achievement, stronger drive, and better behavior (Deslandes & Royer, 2020). According to research, family involvement in schooling has numerous advantages. Kim (2020), for example, discovered that parental involvement in distant learning can improve children's learning by giving emotional and academic support. Additional research has showed that parental involvement can boost children's school engagement and reduce absenteeism (Deslandes & Royer, 2020).

The role of parents in the new normal education, according to Malipot (2020), is critical. They are accountable for ensuring that their children's education continues despite any difficulties. This involves providing equipment and internet access, assisting with assignments, and explaining lessons that may have been missed during online classes. Furthermore, a UNESCO (2020) study stressed the importance of parental involvement in distance learning. According to the study, parental participation boosted children's academic progress and helped them stay on track with their studies. Another study, conducted by Rokhmawati and Nurfitriyani (2021), discovered that parents who actively participate in their children's distant learning have a beneficial impact on their academic achievement.

Regardless of the many advantages of parental involvement, there are certain drawbacks to consider. One key problem is that not all parents have the resources, skills, or time to assist their children's learning while they are participating in distant learning. Parents who work long hours, have several children, or lack the requisite equipment and internet access may find it tough to provide the support that their children need (Kim, 2020). Furthermore, parents

who do not speak the language of instruction may struggle to communicate with teachers and assist their children's learning (Deslandes & Royer, 2020). Studies have shown that parental involvement in education is linked to improved academic achievement and better student behavior (Henderson & Mapp, 2002). This is especially true during the pandemic, where parents have had to take on a more active role in their children's education.

A study conducted by the World Bank discovered that parental involvement in their children's studying throughout the epidemic was related with improved academic performance (World Bank, 2021). Many parents have had to combine their own employment obligations while also ensuring that their children are keeping up with their schoolwork. As a result, parents have had to learn new skills to help their children with their education from home, such as creating a suitable learning environment and providing technical support for online classes. Mothers have always been involved in their children's education, but the pandemic has heightened their importance. With children learning from home, parents have had to take on the role of learning facilitators. According to research conducted by The Learning Agency (2020), parents have been required to become more involved in their children's education and to learn new skills to support their children's learning at home. This includes creating a positive learning atmosphere, assisting with homework, and evaluating their child's progress. According to the survey, parents have had to learn new skills to help their children learn at home, such as fixing technical issues and adapting to new teaching methods. Furthermore, parents have been required to take a more active role in assisting their children with academics, with many spending more time assisting with homework assignments and reviewing lesson plans.

Methodology

This research utilized a qualitative research design to examine the experiences and obstacles faced by parents in supporting their children's distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in basic education. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with a purposive sample of ten parents, comprising two parents from Grade 1, two parents from kindergarten, two from Grade 3, two parents from Grade 4, one parent from Grade 7, and one parent from Grade 11. The interviews were conducted during September and October of 2021, with the goal of generating full and detailed accounts of parents'

experiences with remote learning. Purposive sampling allowed for the identification of participants with various experiences and perspectives relevant to the research questions. Furthermore, the semi-structured nature of the interviews allowed for an exploration of the specific issues faced by parents in supporting their children's schooling during the pandemic while also enabling for flexibility in the data gathering process.

While severe lockdowns were in place, the interviews were done online via video call, and each session lasted between 30 and 45 minutes. The open-ended questions focused on the challenges that parents faced in supporting their children's learning, their perceptions of their ability to support their children's education, how they balanced the demands of supporting their children's education with other responsibilities, the types of support and resources they required, communication with teachers and school administrators, and the potential long-term effects of the pandemic on parent involvement. The data were analyzed using thematic analysis, which involved identifying recurring themes and patterns in the data. The analysis process began with familiarization with the data, followed by generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the final report.

Results and Discussion

The study sought to investigate the experiences of parents as learning facilitators during the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic. The research utilized thematic analysis to determine five key themes that included the experiences of the chosen participants. The first theme, "Change in Daily Routine," highlighted the significant impact of the pandemic on the daily lives of parents and their children. The second theme, "Untrained to Teach," revealed the challenges that parents encountered in facilitating their children's learning due to a lack of formal training in education. The third theme, "Lack of Technological Resources," underscored the difficulties that parents faced in accessing and utilizing technology for distance learning. The fourth theme, "Learning with Child" expressed that they have learned and grown together with their child while facilitating distance learning, leading to a deeper and more meaningful relationship. Finally, "Appreciation toward education sector facilitators," highlighted the parents' positive appreciation towards the efforts of educators and the education sector in adapting to the challenges posed by the pandemic.

Change in Daily Routine

The research revealed a considerable change in the everyday routines of parents and/or guardians prior to and throughout the Covid-19 pandemic. Prior to the epidemic, the majority of their daily activities revolved around domestic tasks like as errands, dinner preparation, and sending and retrieving their children from school. While some parents reported being able to manage work and quality time with their children, the pandemic has forced them to be more hands-on in directing their children's online learning and accomplishing academic tasks. This additional demand on their time has complicated the already difficult challenge of juggling domestic obligations and child-rearing.

In the study results, seven out of ten respondents said that they found it more difficult to manage their responsibilities since the pandemic, especially when they had to facilitate their child's modules and online classes. The abrupt move to remote learning compelled parents to shoulder the added obligation of supporting their children's education while still managing home responsibilities. This posed a substantial problem for parents who were already working full-time or caring for many children. It was challenging for parents to reconcile competing demands on their time and attention while juggling domestic tasks and teaching children. Parents, for example, had to assist their children with their schooling while simultaneously cooking meals, doing washing, and cleaning the house. As a result, parents were frequently forced to multitask or prioritize certain tasks over others, which could lead to feelings of overload or irritation. During the interview, one parent shared:

“Aasikasuhin muna yung bata tapos hatid, maghuluto ng ulam, mamalengke, tapos magsusundo, tapos gagawin yung assignment. Hindi ako tutok sa pag-aaral ng anak ko dati... Hindi katulad ngayon, mas mahirap kasi ikaw na teacher, ikaw pa yung magulang.”

[“Before, I used to take care of my child first, then bring him/her to school, cook food, go to the market, and then pick him/her up, and then we would do the assigned school work. I wasn't focused on my child's studies before, unlike now. It's harder now because you become the teacher and the parent at the same time.”]

The theme came to be a key finding in this study because the COVID-19 pandemic caused school closures, requiring children to shift to distant learning

at home, with parents required to assume the role of facilitators of learning. This abrupt change had a tremendous influence on parents' daily routines, as they were required to combine work, domestic chores, and aiding their children's learning. This study emphasizes the importance of adaptability and flexibility in parents, who had to make considerable modifications in their daily routines to accommodate the demands of distant learning. Additionally, this finding points to the significance of requiring schools and educational institutions to provide additional assistance to parents in their responsibilities as facilitators of learning, such as by delivering training and resources to help them better handle the demands of distant learning. Overall, it stresses the difficulty experienced by parents in transitioning to the new normal of remote learning and highlights the need for continued support to help them negotiate these unprecedented times.

Untrained to Teach

As schools closed and distance learning became the norm, parents were required to take on the role of facilitators and educators, often without the necessary training or expertise. This sudden shift in responsibility created a challenging learning experience for both the parent and the child, as parents struggled to adapt to new teaching methods and to manage their own competing demands.

Eight out of ten parents admit that they are not trained to facilitate school activities for their children. Some of them have not even finished their own studies. The lack of training and expertise was particularly evident in the areas of curriculum design, instructional strategies, and assessment. Parents had difficulties understanding the substance and structure of their children's lessons, which resulted in irritation and confusion for both parent and kid. Furthermore, the use of technology and online platforms for teaching and learning presented substantial hurdles for parents who were unfamiliar with these tools. In the interview, one kindergarten parent shared the difficulty in teaching a child especially getting their attention:

“Hindi naman kami marunong magturo talaga. Minsan, kami nalang ang sumasagot kasi ang hirap turuan ng kinder (child) ko. Mas okay talaga kapag teacher ang magtuturo kasi mas susunod sila doon kaysa sa samin.”

“We really don't know how to teach. Sometimes, we are the ones answering the questions because it's difficult to teach my kindergarten child. It's better if a

teacher will do the teaching because they will follow them more than us.”

The results from the study underscored the significance of giving parents with the support and training they need to properly enable their children's education during times of crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. These could include focused professional development programs and resources for parents, as well as school-family partnerships to foster strong ties and effective communication channels. We can increase the quality of distant learning experiences and better assist children's academic success by addressing the challenges of unskilled parents.

Without a question, the pandemic has underlined the importance of parents having the essential skills and knowledge to aid their child's learning, especially during times of crisis. According to the conclusions of this study, many parents lack the knowledge and skills needed to properly teach their children, resulting in a difficult learning experience for both the parent and the child. As a result, schools and allied sectors must acknowledge the critical role that parents play in their children's education and give them with the appropriate assistance and resources. Furthermore, even after the pandemic diminishes and schools return to traditional in-person learning, schools and allied sectors must continue to prepare parents for potential future disruptions, such as natural disasters or other emergencies that may necessitate a shift to online or remote learning. This can help parents be more prepared to support their child's education, especially in difficult circumstances. Schools and allied industries may assist ensure that all students, regardless of their circumstances, have access to a high-quality education.

Lack of Technological Resources

During the epidemic, parents faced a huge obstacle in assisting their children's learning due to a dearth of technological means. Many parents claimed that they did not have access to computers and dependable internet connections, which are critical instruments for online learning. Their children were unable to fully participate in online lessons or complete their coursework due to a lack of access. As a result, parents have been forced to use alternative ways, such as printing out modules and physically facilitating their children's learning, which can be time-consuming and difficult. This result points out the value of providing enough access to technology for all kids and families, especially during times of crisis such as the epidemic. The education sector should prepare parents and other

stakeholders by providing the appropriate training and tools to help them navigate and effectively use technology to assist their children's education.

Six out of ten parent respondents in the study admitted to having problems with their children's learning tools required for modular and online classes. Their problem is usually explained as a lack of internet access. Furthermore, the instructions in the modules are difficult for the children to understand, and they find it difficult to contact their teachers for clarification. They must have a load for their child to attend online classes. They occasionally rely on their neighbor's internet connection, but it is insufficient.

The findings that numerous parents reported difficulty obtaining and using technical tools such as computers and a stable internet connection had major consequences. This suggests that a lack of access to these resources can impede the delivery of online learning and limit children's ability to participate in remote education. This can lead to a considerable accomplishment difference between pupils with and without access to technology, with long-term ramifications for their academic and occupational success. Furthermore, this highlights the importance of policies and programs aimed at bridging the digital divide and providing equal access to technology for all kids, regardless of socioeconomic position.

Learning with *Them*

The respondents' experiences during the interview acknowledged a positive side of the problems faced by parents during distant learning. Despite the challenges and stress of overseeing their child's education, many parents have discovered that they have grown and learnt alongside their child. This can lead to a deeper and more meaningful relationship between parent and child, as they work together to overcome hurdles and attain educational goals. It also implies that distance learning can allow parents to become more involved and interested in their child's education, which can have long-term benefits for the child's academic progress and overall well-being.

According to the findings, the experience of facilitating remote learning has had a favorable impact on the relationship between parents and their children. Parents who are more involved in their children's education have the opportunity to learn and grow with their children, resulting in a deeper and more meaningful relationship. Parents are given the opportunity to better understand their child's learning style and obstacles, allowing them to provide more

effective assistance and advice. As a result, it can improve general family dynamics and the academic performance of the child. These implications emphasize the significance of parental involvement in education and the possible benefits it can provide for both the child and the family.

“Aside sa natuturuan ko ‘yung anak ko, natututo din ako eh. Minsan, nagiging joke pa namin sa bahay yung nakalagay sa doon (module content).”

“Aside from teaching my child, I am also learning. Sometimes, what is written in their (module) becomes a joke between us at home.”

The fact that parents are learning and growing together with their child while promoting remote learning has crucial implications for both parents and children. It implies that distance learning can be a good and transforming experience for families, building deeper and more meaningful interactions between parents and their children. It also emphasizes the significance of incorporating parents in the educational process, not just as passive viewers, but as active participants who are learning and developing new abilities alongside their children. This research also highlights the potential of remote learning to foster family bonding and lifetime learning among both parents and children.

This finding underlines the potential benefits of incorporating parents more actively in their child's education for the education system. Because of the pandemic's surge in distant learning, parents have been given a more vital role in their child's education. This research implies that integrating parents in this manner can result in a more meaningful educational experience for both the parent and the child. However, this discovery may serve as a reminder to parents to spend quality time with their children and actively participate in their education. With many parents increasingly working from home and spending more time with their children, this study provides a chance to build family relationships and create a more conducive learning environment at home.

Appreciation toward education sector facilitators

The uncovering of parents' appreciation for education sector facilitators is noteworthy because it emphasizes the critical role that teachers and other education professionals play in the effectiveness of distant learning during the pandemic. Recognizing facilitators' work demonstrates parents' appreciation of the obstacles and complexities involved in delivering education remotely. It also reveals that parents value

the services of teachers and other education sector facilitators in ensuring that their children's education is not disrupted despite the pandemic.

The expression of gratitude towards education sector facilitators by parents can have positive implications for the morale and motivation of teachers and other education professionals. It can also encourage greater collaboration and communication between parents and teachers, which can be beneficial in ensuring that the needs of students are met effectively. Additionally, it can foster a sense of community and partnership between parents and education sector facilitators in supporting the education of children in a challenging time.

“Noong may nagka COVID sa street namin.... Hindi kami pwedeng lumabas talaga noon. kaya iyung teacher ng anak ko ‘yung kumukuha ng module. Doon ko na-realize na hindi talaga biro ang maging teacher lalo na sa public (public school).”

“When a household in our street contracted COVID-19, we were not allowed to go out at all. That's why the teachers were the ones who took my child's module. That's when I realized that being a teacher, especially in the public school, is really no joke.”

In the research, it is significant to note that all (ten out of ten) parent respondents expressed their appreciation toward the education sector facilitators notably the instructors. This conclusion is significant because it emphasizes parents' acknowledgment and appreciation for education sector facilitators who played a critical role in ensuring their children's education continuity during the pandemic. Without a doubt, the epidemic has disrupted traditional modes of schooling and forced a move to remote learning, putting a lot of pressure and problems on both parents and educators. Yet, their recognition and appreciation for the efforts of education sector facilitators can enhance their morale and drive to continue providing great education in the face of adversity. It also underlines the significance of a solid cooperation between parents and education facilitators in guaranteeing distant learning success.

This result has brought to light the barriers and challenges faced by both parents and teachers in maintaining the continuity of education for pupils. It emphasizes the significance of having support mechanisms and resources in place for both parents and teachers in order to effectively allow distant learning, particularly in the setting of a public

education system with limited resources. It also underlines the need of teamwork and cooperation between parents and teachers in resolving these problems and ensuring pupils receive the greatest possible learning outcomes.

Conclusion

According to the results of a study, the pandemic has had a considerable impact on parents' involvement in their children's education, particularly in the context of distance learning. While parents experienced a variety of hurdles in helping their children's learning, such as a lack of technical resources and difficulty comprehending learning materials, they also voiced respect and gratitude to education sector facilitators. Parents also claimed that their involvement in their children's education has resulted in a deeper and more meaningful bond with their child. These findings underscore the necessity of providing assistance and training to parents, as well as education sector facilitators, to enable the proper delivery of distant learning and the continuity of children's education during times of crisis. Moving forward, it is critical to address the issues raised in this study and adopt solutions to assist parents and education sector facilitators in adapting to the changing educational landscape.

It may be argued that the COVID-19 epidemic has had a substantial impact on the education sector, particularly on student education delivery. Remote learning has become the new norm, and parents have been pressed into the role of educational facilitators for their children. According to the survey, parents reported a variety of issues in their new position, including a lack of technology resources, trouble coordinating obligations, and difficulties with their children's learning materials.

The study's results have various implications for education stakeholders. Firstly, it emphasizes the importance of proper training and support for parents in assisting their children's learning, particularly through the use of technology. Second, it emphasizes the significance of having access to technology resources, such as a solid internet connection and computers, in order to facilitate effective distance learning. Finally, it highlights the importance of ongoing communication and cooperation between parents and instructors in order to clarify learning materials and address issues as soon as possible. Ultimately, the study concludes that the pandemic posed unique obstacles to the education industry while

also providing chances for expansion and innovation. The findings of this study are expected to inform the creation of policies and programs that can solve the issues faced by parents and education sector facilitators in guaranteeing quality education for kids in the setting of remote learning.

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